

STUDIES ON THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT FARMING PRACTICES ON SOIL MICROBIAL STATUS AND YIELD OF SOYBEAN (*Glycine max* L.) IN INCEPTISOLS

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted during kharif 2023 at Agronomy farm, College of Agriculture, Pune to study the effect of different farming practices on soil microbial status and yield of soybean (*Glycine max* L.). The experiment was laid out in randomized block design having five treatments with four replications. The treatments comprised T₁ – Farmer's practice, T₂ – MPKV recommended package of practices, T₃ – Organic farming, T₄ – Natural farming and T₅ – Climate resilient farming. The results indicated that among the five farming practices examined, Treatment T₃, which employed organic farming methods, exhibited a significant increase in the population of beneficial microorganisms, including total bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes, *Rhizobium*, PSB, and KMB with values of bacteria 160.58 and 125.58 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil, fungi 26.16 and 17.16 x 10⁵ cfu g⁻¹ soil, actinomycetes 35.58 and 26.16 x 10⁴ cfu g⁻¹ soil, *Rhizobium* 42.66 and 26.83 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil, PSB 39.33 and 28.73 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil and KMB 35.42 and 25.42 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil at 50% flowering and at harvest stage respectively which was statistically at par with the treatments T₂ and T₅. Soil enzyme activities exhibited a progressive increase from treatment T₁ to T₃. Specifically, significant enhancements were observed in: Acid phosphatase, from 6.28 to 9.41 μg PNP g⁻¹ hr⁻¹, alkaline phosphatase 8.11 to 12.13 μg PNP g⁻¹ hr⁻¹, urease enzyme 16.85 to 22.85 μg NH₄⁺ -N g⁻¹ soil hr⁻¹, dehydrogenase 8.20 to 10.02 μg TPF g⁻¹ soil 24 hr⁻¹. These increases indicate a boost in soil enzyme activities under organic farming practices. The highest grain and straw yield were achieved in T₅, with a grain yield of 26.09 q ha⁻¹ and a straw yield of 33.66 q ha⁻¹. Organic farming outperformed Natural Farming, with a grain yield of 11.38 q ha⁻¹ and a straw yield of 15.02 q ha⁻¹. The study concluded that organic farming practices had a positive impact on soil biological properties in the first year, without any negative effects on soil health. Lower yields in organic farming were noted during the first year as more time is needed for organic practices to become fully effective.

Keywords: Soybean, Organic farming, Soil biological properties, farming practices, yield.

Introduction

Soybean (*Glycine max* L.) a legume crop plays a crucial role in global food security and sustainable agriculture. Soybean crop is most important source of protein, fatty acid, lecithin, vitamin A and D. It also contains 30% carbohydrates and 4% fiber. The crops productivity and sustainability are closely related with the soil health, which influenced by various farming practices. Although chemical fertilizers are essential for meeting the nutritional needs of crops, their prolonged use can have detrimental consequences on the physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of soil, ultimately impacting crop yields (Sarkar *et al.* 1997). Intensive farming practices can degrade soil health, leading to reduce soil fertility, decreased crop yields, and environmental concerns.

Under the different crop management practices, organic farming leads to higher soil quality than conventional farming due to improved soil biodiversity, soil structure, use of bio-fertilizers, increased microbial biomass, increased enzymes activity. Soil quality is measured using a range of chemical and biological parameters. In that, Microbial Biomass Nitrogen (MBN) and the availability of different soil enzymes are the most effective indicators for monitoring the productivity and quality of soil. Soil microorganisms are essential for maintaining soil fertility and ecosystem. This research investigated the properties of six soil microorganisms, specifically bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes, PSB (Phosphate Solubilizing Bacteria), KMB (Potassium Mobilizing Bacteria) and *Rhizobium*. Soil enzymes serve as catalysts for energy transfer, mediating the conversion of organic matter into nutrient-rich compounds. These are easily measured and integrate information on both the microbial status and physiochemical soil conditions. Soil enzyme activities quickly reflect changes in soil management practices (Aon *et al.* 2001). There are various types of soil enzymes found in soil. From these, four enzyme activities are studied in this research namely urease, dehydrogenase, acid phosphatase and alkaline phosphatase.

Therefore, soil microbial study and soil enzyme assay are the most important aspects of Agriculture. These factors improve soils physical properties and promotes its stabilization. Presently, there is a growing concern among the farmers to adopt different farming practices which improve soil health by improving biological properties and it also increases crop productivity. To meet this demand, various farming practices adopted by the farmers from the preparation of soil to the harvesting of the crop are farmer's practices, organic farming

practices, climate resilient farming practices, natural farming practices, etc. Being a leguminous crop, soybean can fix atmospheric nitrogen with the help of *Rhizobium* which act as a symbiotic atmospheric nitrogen fixer found in root nodules of legumes. Investigating biological activities in soils is essential, as they serve as indicators of the soil's potential to sustain biochemical processes critical for maintaining soil fertility. Hence, the experiment on "Studies on the effect of different farming practices on the soil microbial status and yield of soybean (*Glycine max* L.)" was proposed with the following objectives:

1. To estimate the periodical population of microorganisms in soil.
2. To study soil enzymatic activities under different farming practices.

Materials And Method:

The field experiment was conducted during Kharif 2023 at the plot no.15, Agronomy Farm, College of Agriculture, Pune, Dist.- Pune (Maharashtra). The soil of experimental sites was medium black in colour and well drained, with a uniform depth up to 90 cm. To determine the biological composition of the soil of the experimental site, root nodules and rhizosphere soil of soybean were selected as a source sample for isolating microorganisms and analysis of soil enzymes. The soil samples were collected from different locations of field plot. The individual plants were uprooted and root nodules and soil intact with roots was later used for isolation purpose.

Treatment details

The soybean variety KDS-726 (Phule Sangam) was grown as a test crop.

The field experiment comprised following treatments.

Farmers practice (T1):

Basal dose of 10:26:26 N, P₂O₅ and K₂O kg ha⁻¹@250 kg ha⁻¹, Two foliar sprays of 19:19:19 @ 2 % at 21 and 35 DAS.

MPKV recommended package of practice (T2):

RDF (50:75:45 kg ha⁻¹ N, P₂O₅, and K₂O), Application of FYM @ 10 t ha⁻¹ (Basal application), Seed treatment of biofertilizers viz., *Rhizobium*+ Phosphate solubilizing bacteria+ Potash solubilizing bacteria consortium @ 25 ml kg⁻¹ of seeds.

Organic farming (T3):

Basal application of FYM @10 t ha⁻¹, Vermicompost @ 3.5 t ha⁻¹ and Phosphate rich organic manure (PROM) @ 200 kg ha⁻¹, Seed treatment of biofertilizers viz., *Rhizobium* + Phosphate solubilizing bacteria + Potash solubilizing bacteria consortium @ 25 ml kg⁻¹ of seeds.

Natural farming (T4):

Soil application of Jeevamrit @ 2000 kg ha⁻¹ during sowing, Mixed cropping system broadcasting of jowar and maize @ 12 kg ha⁻¹, Seed treatment of Beejamrit and drying of seeds in shade, After sowing mulching of crop residues of previous crop, After sowing application of 500 L ha⁻¹ Jeevamrit with first two irrigations, Foliar sprays of Jeevamrit (12.5 L ha⁻¹ Jeevamrit + 250 L of water at 21 DAS, 19 L ha⁻¹ Jeevamrit + 300 L of water at 45 DAS, 25 L ha⁻¹ Jeevamrit + 375 L of water at 65 DAS, 37.5 L ha⁻¹ Jeevamrit + 375 L of water at 80 DAS), 7.5 L ha⁻¹ Sour Buttermilk + 250 L of water at 90 DAS.

Climate resilient farming (T5):

Sowing of soybean on BBF (Broad Bed Furrow), Application of chemical fertilizers as per STCRC target 35 qt ha⁻¹, Basal application No. of specific microorganisms per g of soil = Average plate count x Dilution factor

of FYM@10 t ha⁻¹ Seed treatment of biofertilizers viz., *Rhizobium* + Phosphate solubilizing bacteria+ Potash solubilizing bacteria consortium @ 25 ml kg⁻¹ of seeds, Mulching of weed/crop residues.

Isolation of Microorganisms

The total number of bacteria, actinomycetes, fungi, *Rhizobium*, PSB and KMB from soil and root nodules were recorded by Serial Dilution Pour Plate Method. Counted the number of bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes, *Rhizobium*, PSB and KMB colonies in each plate and calculated the average number of microorganisms per gram of soil by multiplying the average count per plate by the dilution factor and dividing by the oven-dry weight of one gram soil sample by the following formula:

$$\text{No. of specific microorganisms per g of soil} = \frac{\text{Average plate count} \times \text{Dilution factor}}{\text{Weight of soil sample taken}}$$

Assay of soil enzymes:

The activities of soil enzymes viz., urease, dehydrogenase, acid and alkaline phosphatase were measured by using standard methods.

Sr. No.	Enzyme	Method	Reference
1.	Urease	Titrimetry	Tabatabai and Bremner (1972)
2.	Dehydrogenase	Spectrophotometry	Casida <i>et al.</i> (1964)
3.	Acid Phosphatase	Spectrophotometry	Evazi and Tabatabai (1977)
4	Alkaline Phosphatase	Spectrophotometry	Evazi and Tabatabai (1977)

Observations Recorded:

Microbial Population

At initial (Before sowing) 2. At 50% flowering 3. After harvesting

Soil Enzyme activity

At initial (Before sowing) 2. At 50% flowering 3. After harvesting A randomized block design (RBD) with analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to assess treatment effects on all studied characteristics (Panse and Sukhatme, 1985)

Results And Discussion:

Soil Microbial population at 50 percent flowering and at harvest time of soybean crop:

The results (Table1) revealed that among the five different farming practices, the treatment T₃ organic farming practice showed appreciable increase in population of total bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes, *Rhizobium*, PSB, and KMB. The range values of bacteria were 160.58 and 125.58 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil, fungi 26.16 and 17.16 x 10⁵ cfu g⁻¹ soil, actinomycetes 35.58 and 26.16 x 10⁴ cfu g⁻¹ soil, *Rhizobium* 42.66 and 26.83 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil, PSB 39.33 and 28.73 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil, and KMB 35.42 and 25.42 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil at 50% flowering and at harvest stage respectively. The above values showed that microbial population exhibited a peak during flowering stage of soybean crop, indicating a surge in microbial activity at this stage. However, a slight reduction in microbial population was observed at the harvest stage of the soybean crop.

According to (Chang *et al.* 2007) soil microbial biomass, population of bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes, as well as enzyme activity increased significantly in the compost treated soil compared with the chemical fertilizer treated soil. These results were similar with the findings showed that soil microorganisms mainly rely on organic carbon for food and energy. When organic materials are added to the soil, they break down and release energy, which helps to increase the number of beneficial microbes in the soil (Ingle *et al.* 2014). The treatment T₃ showed significantly higher microbial population at all stages of soybean crop which was statistically at par with the treatments T₂ MPKV recommended package of practices and T₅ climate resilient farming. While, the treatment T₁ farmers practice had lower microbial population of bacteria 136.33 and 111.83 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil, fungi 15.41 and 11.66 x 10⁵ cfu g⁻¹ soil, actinomycetes 24.33 and 18.33 x 10⁴ cfu g⁻¹ soil, *Rhizobium* 33.08 and 14.66 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil, PSB 18.91 and 14.08 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil and KMB 13.16 and 10.33 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil at 50% flowering and harvest stage respectively. Therefore, the treatment T₃ organic farming which comprises of the application of FYM, vermicompost along with biofertilizers found to improve the soil microbial status at all stages of soybean crop.

Soil enzyme activity at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest of soybean crop:

The soil enzyme activities progressively increased from the treatment T₁ to T₃ (Table 2). The significant increase in acid phosphatase 6.28 (T₁) to 9.41 µg PNP g⁻¹ hr⁻¹ (T₃); alkaline phosphatase 8.11 (T₁) to 12.13 µg PNP g⁻¹ hr⁻¹ (T₃); urease 16.85 (T₁) to 22.85 µg NH₄⁺ -N g⁻¹ soil hr⁻¹ (T₃); dehydrogenase 8.20 (T₁) to 10.02 µg TPF g⁻¹ soil 24 hr⁻¹ (T₃). The activities of soil enzymes showed a significant increase from treatment T₁ to T₃, with the significant increase in T₃. The application of organic manures and fertilizers had a stimulating effect on soil enzyme activity, which led to improved soil fertility and overall soil health. Enzyme activity reaches its highest level during the flowering stage, coinciding with the crop's rapid growth phase. During this period, root activity increases, leading to the release of enzymes like urease and phosphatase into the soil, resulting in enhanced nutrient mineralization. Hence the above results are in agreement with the results of Verma *et al.* (2018).

These results are similar with the results observed by (Gorge, 2022) who stated that release of organic acids during the solubilization of nutrients can lead to a slight acidification of the soil, creating an environment that is more favorable for enzyme activity. Our result is in consistent with the findings of (Saha, 2008) who indicated that organic manure had a positive effect on urease activity

Yield of soybean under different farming practices:

The highest grain and straw yield were (Table 3) recorded in the T₅ Climate Resilient Farming treatment, which achieved a grain yield of 26.09 q ha⁻¹, and straw yield 33.66 q ha⁻¹. In contrast, the treatment T₄ natural farming resulted in the lowest yield, with 8.05 and 10.07 q ha⁻¹ grain and straw yield respectively. Organic farming outperformed natural farming, with 11.38 and 15.02 q ha⁻¹ grain and straw yield respectively.

Organic farming often experiences lower yields in the first year due to several factors. The soil takes time to adjust to new organic practices, leading to a temporary decline in fertility and structure. Additionally, organic farming relies on natural nutrient sources, which may not be readily available or sufficient in the first year (Lotter *et al.*, 2003). Hence, our results presented above align with the existing research confirming that organic farming treatment exhibit lower yield in the first year over time, as the soil ecosystem matures, yields may improve significantly.

Conclusion:

Results of the investigation demonstrated a strong correlation between farming practices and microbial population dynamics, as well as soil enzyme activity.

It was concluded that the practices applied to organic farming were beneficial for improvement of soil biological properties without any adverse effect on soil health during the first year of study.

The adoption of organic and recommended farming practices can lead to improved soil health, supporting sustainable crop production. The lower yields in organic farming practices was recorded in the first year can be attributed to factors such as nutrient availability, soil health, pest pressures, and the time required for organic practices to take full effect. Over time, as the soil ecosystem matures, yields may improve significantly.

These results were based on the field experiment conducted during one season of soybean crop which may suggested to be continued in the subsequent year to ascertain the effect of different farming practices on soil quality and yield of soybean crop.

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Table 1. Effect of different farming practices on microbial population in soil at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest of soybean

Treat. No.	Farming practices	Microbial populatiopn											
		Bacteria ($\times 10^6$ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)		Fungi ($\times 10^5$ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)		Actinomycetes ($\times 10^4$ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)		<i>Rhizobium</i> ($\times 10^6$ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)		PSB ($\times 10^6$ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)		KMB ($\times 10^6$ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)	
		At 50% flowering	At harvest	At 50% flowering	At harvest	At 50% flowering	At harvest	At 50% flowering	At harvest	At 50% flowering	At harvest	At 50% flowering	At harvest
T1	Farmers practice	136.33	111.83	15.41	11.66	24.33	18.33	33.08	14.66	18.91	14.08	13.16	10.33
T2	MPKV recommended package of practice	154.16	123.16	24.16	15.91	33.91	22.66	39.41	24.33	37.91	26.16	33.41	22.00
T3	Organic farming	160.58	125.58	26.16	17.16	35.58	26.16	42.66	26.83	39.33	28.73	35.42	25.42
T4	Natural farming	149.91	110.83	21.33	14.08	26.00	21.33	35.41	16.91	23.66	17.41	19.41	11.33
T5	Climate resilient farming	154.66	124.25	24.58	16.08	32.50	23.91	38.58	22.91	37.83	28.41	32.66	24.66
	SE(m) \pm	3.01	2.90	0.97	0.62	1.61	1.26	1.35	2.85	1.83	1.78	1.63	1.59
	CD (0.05)	9.28	8.93	2.98	1.90	4.97	3.89	4.17	8.78	5.64	5.49	5.01	4.89
	Initial	81.58		9.12		11.16		-		10.33		9.83	

Table 2. Effect of farming practices on enzymatic activities in soil at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest of soybean crop

Treat. No.	Farming practices	Dehydrogenase enzyme ($\mu\text{g TPF g}^{-1}$ soil 24 hr ⁻¹)		Alkaline phosphatase enzyme ($\mu\text{g PNP g}^{-1}$ hr ⁻¹)		Acid phosphatase enzyme ($\mu\text{g PNP g}^{-1}$ hr ⁻¹)		Urease enzyme ($\mu\text{g NH}^+ \text{-N g}^{-1}$ soil hr ⁻¹) ⁴	
		At 50% flowering	At harvest	At 50% flowering	At harvest	At 50% flowering	At harvest	At 50% flowering	At harvest
T1	Farmers practice	8.20	7.25	8.11	7.44	6.28	5.53	16.85	14.47
T2	MPKV recommended package of practice	9.65	9.27	11.57	11.05	8.95	8.44	21.57	18.95
T3	Organic farming	10.02	9.82	12.13	11.30	9.41	8.70	22.85	19.95
T4	Natural farming	8.37	7.75	9.38	8.67	7.71	7.15	19.97	17.67
T5	Climate resilient farming	9.82	9.32	11.67	11.01	8.97	8.40	21.47	18.82
	SE(m) \pm	0.20	0.20	0.22	0.14	0.16	0.13	0.46	0.49
	CD (0.05)	0.63	0.64	0.68	0.43	0.51	0.43	1.43	1.53
	Initial	7.20	-	7.23	-	6.12	-	12.35	-

Table 3: Effect of different farming practices on yield of soybean.

Treatment No.	Farming practices	Yield (qha ⁻¹)	
		Grain	Straw
T ₁	Farmer's practice	19.05	24.00
T ₂	MPKV recommended package of practices	22.82	29.44
T ₃	Organic farming	11.83	15.02
T ₄	Natural farming	8.05	10.07
T ₅	Climate resilient farming	26.09	33.66
	SE(m) \pm	0.97	1.24
	CD (5%)	3.02	3.87